

Patterns of Integer Solutions to Homogeneous Ternary Quadratic Equation

$$ax^2 + by^2 = (a+b)(c^2 + ab)z^2$$

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Abstract

This paper aims at determining many non-zero distinct integer solutions to the homogeneous ternary quadratic Diophantine equation $ax^2 + by^2 = (a+b)(c^2 + ab)z^2$, where a, b are non-zero distinct positive integers and the product $a*b$ is square-free. Substitution technique and factorization method are utilized to obtain the patterns of solutions in integers for the given homogeneous ternary quadratic equation.

Keywords: Homogeneous quadratic equation, Ternary quadratic equation, Integer solutions, Transformation technique, Factorization method

Introduction

It is quite obvious that Diophantine equations, one of the areas of number theory, are rich in variety [1,2]. In particular, the ternary quadratic Diophantine equations in connection with geometrical figures occupy a pivotal role in the orbit of mathematics and have a wealth of historical significance. These types of equations are significant since they geometrically represent three dimensional figures namely cones. These solutions play a vital role in different area of mathematics & science and help us in understanding the significance of number patterns. The theoretical importance of quadratic equations in three unknowns with integral coefficients is great as they are closely connected with many problems of number theory. Specifically, the second degree homogeneous equations with three unknowns occupy a pivotal role in the region of mathematics. It is well-known that the quadratic Diophantine equations, homogeneous or non-homogeneous, have aroused the interest of many mathematicians. In particular, one may refer [3-15] for quadratic equations with three unknowns representing different geometrical figures. The above problems motivated us to search for the distinct integer solutions to ternary homogeneous quadratic equations.

In this paper, a typical ternary quadratic Diophantine equation representing cone given by $a x^2 + b y^2 = (a + b) (c^2 + a b) z^2$ is studied for determining its integer solutions successfully through elementary algebra, namely, substitution strategy and factorization method.

Method of analysis

The homogeneous ternary quadratic equation to be solved is

$$a x^2 + b y^2 = (a + b)(c^2 + a b)z^2 \tag{1}$$

In the above equation (1), a, b take non-zero distinct positive integer values such that the product a b is square-free and c is any non-zero integer. The option

$$x = X + bT, y = X - aT \tag{2} \text{ in (1)}$$

leads to the ternary quadratic equation

$$X^2 + a b T^2 = (c^2 + a b)z^2 \tag{3}$$

The procedure to obtain patterns of integer solutions to (1) through employing the solutions to (3) is illustrated below:

Procedure 1

By inspection, it is seen that, the assumption

$$X = c z, T = z \tag{4} \text{ satisfies}$$

(3). In view of (2), observe that the solutions to (1) are given by

$$x = (c + b) z, y = (c - a) z \tag{5}$$

Procedure 2

Express (3) in the form of ratio as

$$\frac{X + c z}{a(z + T)} = \frac{b(z - T)}{X - c z} = \frac{\alpha}{\beta}, \beta \neq 0 \tag{6}$$

which is equivalent to the system of double equations

$$\begin{aligned} \beta X - a \alpha T + (\beta c - a \alpha) z &= 0 \\ \alpha X + b \beta T - (\alpha c + b \beta) z &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Solving the above system by employing the method of cross-multiplication, one has

$$\begin{aligned} X &= a c \alpha^2 - b c \beta^2 + 2 a b \alpha \beta \\ T &= -a \alpha^2 + b \beta^2 + 2 c \alpha \beta \\ z &= b \beta^2 + a \alpha^2 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

In view of (2), one has

$$\begin{aligned} x &= a(c-b)\alpha^2 + b(b-c)\beta^2 + 2b(a+c)\alpha\beta \\ y &= a(c+a)\alpha^2 - b(c+a)\beta^2 + 2a(b-c)\alpha\beta \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Thus, the values of x, y, z given by (8) & (7) satisfy (1).

Procedure 3

Let

$$z = p^2 + a b q^2 \tag{9}$$

Substitute (9) in (3). Applying factorization and equating the positive factors, consider

$$\begin{aligned} X + i\sqrt{ab}T &= (c + i\sqrt{ab})(p + i\sqrt{ab}q)^2 \\ &= (c + i\sqrt{ab})[f(p, q) + i\sqrt{ab}g(p, q)] \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

where

$$f(p, q) = p^2 - a b q^2, g(p, q) = 2 p q \tag{11}$$

Equating the real and imaginary parts in (10), one has

$$\begin{aligned} X &= c f(p, q) - a b g(p, q) \\ T &= f(p, q) + c g(p, q) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, in view of (2), we get

$$\begin{aligned} x &= (c + b) f(p, q) + b(c - a) g(p, q) \\ y &= (c - a) f(p, q) - a(b + c) g(p, q) \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Therefore, the values of x, y, z given by (12) & (9) satisfy (1).

Procedure 4

Write (3) as

$$X^2 + a b T^2 = (c^2 + a b) z^2 * 1 \tag{13}$$

The integer 1 on the R.H.S. of (13) is expressed as

$$1 = \frac{[a b r^2 - s^2 + i \sqrt{a b} 2 r s][a b r^2 - s^2 - i \sqrt{a b} 2 r s]}{(a b r^2 + s^2)^2} \quad (14)$$

Assume

$$z = (a b r^2 + s^2)^2 (p^2 + a b q^2) \quad (15)$$

Substitute (14) and (15) in (13). Employing the method of factorization and equating the positive factors on both sides, one has

$$X + i \sqrt{a b} T = (a b r^2 + s^2)(c + i \sqrt{a b}) [F(p, q, a, b, r, s) + i \sqrt{a b} G(p, q, a, b, r, s)] \quad (16)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} F(p, q, a, b, r, s) &= (a b r^2 - s^2) f(p, q) - 2 a b r s g(p, q) \\ G(p, q, a, b, r, s) &= (a b r^2 - s^2) g(p, q) + 2 r s f(p, q) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Equating the coefficients of the corresponding terms in (16), one has

$$\begin{aligned} X &= (a b r^2 + s^2) [c F(p, q, a, b, r, s) - a b G(p, q, a, b, r, s)] \\ T &= (a b r^2 + s^2) [F(p, q, a, b, r, s) + c G(p, q, a, b, r, s)] \end{aligned}$$

From (2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} x &= (a b r^2 + s^2)[(c + b) F(p, q, a, b, r, s) + b(c - a) G(p, q, a, b, r, s)] \\ y &= (a b r^2 + s^2)[(c - a) F(p, q, a, b, r, s) - a(c + b) G(p, q, a, b, r, s)] \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Thus, (1) is satisfied by (15) and (18).

Procedure 5

Rewrite (3) as

$$(c^2 + a b) z^2 - X^2 = a b T^2 \quad (19)$$

Take

$$T = (c^2 + a b) p^2 - q^2 \quad (20)$$

Consider

$$a b = (\sqrt{c^2 + a b} + c) (\sqrt{c^2 + a b} - c) \quad (21)$$

Substitute (20) & (21) in (19). Utilizing factorization and equating positive

factors on both sides, we get

$$\begin{aligned}\sqrt{c^2 + a b} z + X &= (\sqrt{c^2 + a b + c}) (\sqrt{c^2 + a b} p + q)^2 \\ &= (\sqrt{c^2 + a b + c}) [(c^2 + a b)p^2 + q^2 + 2 p q \sqrt{c^2 + a b}]\end{aligned}$$

On equating the corresponding terms in the above equation, one has

$$\begin{aligned}z &= (c^2 + a b)p^2 + q^2 + 2 p q c \\ X &= c[(c^2 + a b)p^2 + q^2] + 2 p q (c^2 + a b)\end{aligned}\tag{22}$$

In view of (2) , we have

$$\begin{aligned}x &= (c + b)(c^2 + a b)p^2 + (c - b)q^2 + 2 p q (c^2 + a b) \\ y &= (c - a)(c^2 + a b)p^2 + (c + a)q^2 + 2 p q (c^2 + a b)\end{aligned}\tag{23}$$

Thus, the values of x, y, z given by (23) & (22) satisfy (1).

Conclusion

In this paper an attempt has been made to obtain many non-zero distinct integer solutions to the homogeneous ternary quadratic Diophantine equation $a x^2 + b y^2 = (a + b)(c^2 + a b) z^2$, where a, b are non-zero distinct positive integers and the product $a \cdot b$ is square-free. As quadratic equations are rich in variety, the researchers in this field may search for integer solutions to other choices of quadratic equations with multiple variables.

References:

- [1] L.E. Dickson, History of Theory of Numbers, Vol.2, Chelsea Publishing Company, New York, 1952. <https://archive.org/details/historyoftheoryo01dick/page/n1/mode/2up>
- [2] L.J.Mordell, Diophantine equations, Academic press, New York, 1969. [Diophantine Equations. By L. J. Mordell. Pp. 312. 1969. 90s. \(Academic Press, London & New York.\) |The Mathematical Gazette | Cambridge Core](#)
- [3] M.A.Gopalan, D.Geetha, Lattice Points on the Hyperboloid of Two sheets $x^2 - 6xy + y^2 + 6x - 2y + 5 = z^2 + 4$, Impact J.Sci. Tech, Vol. 4(1), Pp. 23-32, 2010.
- [4] M.A.Gopalan, S.Vidhyalakshmi and T.R.Usharani, Integral Points on the Non-homogeneous Cone $2z^2 + 4xy + 8x - 4z + 2 = 0$, Global Journal of Mathematics and Mathematical Sciences, Vol. 2(1), Pp. 61-67, 2012. <https://www.ripublication.com/Volume/gjmmsv2n1.htm>
- [5] M.A.Gopalan, S.Vidhyalakshmi and N.Thiruniraiselvi, Observations on the ternary quadratic Diophantine equation $x^2 + 9y^2 = 50z^2$, International Journal of Applied Research, Vol.1(2), Pp.51-53, 2015. <https://www.allresearchjournal.com/archives/2015/vol1issue2/PartB/60.1-590.pdf>
- [6] M.A.Gopalan, S.Vidhyalakshmi and N.Thiruniraiselvi, Construction of Diophantine quadruple through the integer solution of ternary quadratic Diophantine equation $x^2 + y^2 = z^2 + 4n$, International Journal of Innovative Research in Engineering and Science, Vol.5(4), Pp.1-7, May-2015

- [7] M.A.Gopalan, S.Vidhyalakshmi and N.Thiruniraiselvi, Observations on the cone $z^2 = ax^2 + a(a-1)y^2$, International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development, Vol.2 (9), Pp.304-305, Sep-2015. <https://www.allsubjectjournal.com/assets/archives/2015/vol2issue9/164.pdf>
- [8] M.A.Gopalan, S.Vidhyalakshmi and N.Thiruniraiselvi, A Study on Special Homogeneous Cone $z^2 = 24x^2 + y^2$, Vidyabharati International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, (Special Issue on "Recent Research Trends in Management, Science and Technology"-Part-3, pdf page- 330), Pg: 1203-1208, 2021. <https://www.viirj.org/specialissues/SP10/Part%203.pdf>
- [9] M.A. Gopalan, S. Vidhyalakshmi and N. Thiruniraiselvi, On the Homogeneous Ternary Quadratic Diophantine Equation $6x^2 + 5y^2 = 341z^2$, Vidyabharati International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, (Special Issue on "Recent Research Trends in Management, Science and Technology"-Part-4, pdf page- 318), Pg: 1612-1617, 2021. <https://www.viirj.org/specialissues/SP10/Part%204.pdf>
- [10] M.A. Gopalan, S. Vidhyalakshmi and N. Thiruniraiselvi, A class of new solutions in integers to Ternary Quadratic Diophantine Equation $12(x^2 + y^2) - 23xy + 2x + 2y + 4 = 56z^2$, International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews, Vol 5 (5), Page – 3224-3226, May (2024). https://www.ijrpr.com/current_issues.php
- [11] M.A.Gopalan , S.Vidhyalakshmi., J.Shanthi.J, V.Anbuvalli., On Finding the integer Solutions of Ternary Quadratic Diophantine Equation $3(x^2 + y^2) - 5xy = 36z^2$, International Journal of Precious Engineering Research and Application(IJPERA), volume 7, Issue 1 , May 2022,34-38. <https://www.ijpera.org/papers/Vol-7iss-1/H07013438.pdf>
- [12] J.Shanthi, M.Parkavi. "On Finding Integer Solutions To The Homogeneous Ternary Quadratic Diophantine Equation $2(x^2 + y^2) - 3xy = 32z^2$ " International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews, Vol 4, no 1, January 2023,pp 700-708. <https://ijrpr.com/uploads/V4ISSUE1/IJRPR9407.pdf>
- [13] J.Shanthi., V.Anbuvalli., M.A.Gopalan,S.Vidhyalakshmi, On finding integer solutions to the homogeneous cone $x^2 + (k^2 + 2k)y^2 = (k+1)^4 z^2$, International Journal of Mathematics and computer Research, Volume 11, Issue 07, July 2023,Pp 3555-3557. <https://ijmcr.in/index.php/ijmcr/article/view/597>
- [14] J.Shanthi, M.A.Gopalan , A Glimpse on Homogeneous Ternary Quadratic Diophantine Equation $39(x^2 + y^2) + 72xy = 246z^2$, IARJSET,11(9),2024,96-101. <https://iarjset.com/papers/a-glimpse-on-homogeneous-ternary-quadratic-diophantine-equation/>
- [15] R.Loganayaki, S.Mallika, Observation on the Ternary Quadratic Diophantine Equation $13x^2 + 3y^2 = 640z^2$, IRJEdT,2(3),2021,14-25